

**DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF A WEB-BASED DISCUSSION FORUM FOR
COMPUTER SCIENCE STUDENTS**

A

PROJECT PRESENTED

BY

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**PROJECT WORK SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTER
SCIENCE, FACULTY OF SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF ABUJA, IN PARTIAL
FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENT FOR THE AWARD OF BACHELOR
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MAY, 2021.

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the project work entitled “Design and Implementation of a Web-Based discussion Forum for computer science students ” is a collection of my original research work and it has not been presented for any other qualification anywhere. Information from other sources (published or unpublished) has been duly acknowledged.

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CERTIFICATION PAGE

This is to certify that this project work “Design and Implementation of a Web-Based discussion Forum for computer science students” was carried out by with Matric Number 17283102 meets the regulations governing the award of the degree of Bachelor of Science in Computer Science of the University of Abuja and it is approved for its contribution to scientific Knowledge and literary presentation.

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DEDICATION

This project work is dedicated to ALMIGHTY GOD who through his infinite mercy, love, grace, and kindness has been my source of inspiration till the end of this project work, and my wonderful and supporting Sister, Ms. Joy Ebri.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I give all thanks to God for the gift of life, infinite love, and the successful completion of this project. My greatest motivator is my Aunt, Dr Anne Ebri. I appreciate your words of encouragement and all of the daily prayers you have said for me. Thank you so much for always being there for me! I appreciate all my family members that supported me. My deepest appreciation to my wonderful professors, who have accompanied my studies for the last four years, and to my supervisor, Prof. Owolabi Olumide for all of his support, care, and commitment in guiding me through the composition of my project, you inspired me to become a better professional every day. Thanks to Segun Oladiran, my Friends and colleagues who gave me the support I needed to get here

ABSTRACT

The world is fast becoming a global village due to the effect of globalization and rapid growth in technology. This has enabled information sharing among various people of the world, thereby solving basic societal problems and bringing about rapid development. The study designs and implements a web-based forum where computer science students of the University of Abuja, or various universities in Nigeria and the world at large can come together and interact online. Various web bases/categories such as programming, web development, networking, computer repairs/maintenance, android/IOS discussions, phone, and technology, in general, can be integrated into this online forum. Faced with the challenges many computer science students face when trying to execute some of their projects, the researcher deem it fit to create a social platform where students can register, log in, ask Information Technology questions, and get quality answers from users and admin, create numerous computer and ICT related topics to inform others and get others to read their thoughts and projects and reply or like their post. Concerning methodology, the system was created using PHP and MySQL. The aim of the system is to create a discussion forum where users can create various topics, reply topics and moderate topics by the administrator of the site or super moderators.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The advancement in technologies and the fast pace of globalization have led to university students either partially or fully participating in an online environment (LaPointe et al, 2008). Online learning presents not only challenges in course design but also opportunities to enhance student learning. The value of online learning communities is supported by powerful learning theories; an active learning community and a sense of connectedness to others are critical to real learning (Reisetter et al, 2008). The recent growth in computer networks and more specifically, the World Wide Web (WWW) has given rise to communication, socialization, and interaction between individuals via the Internet. The internet is being used for several purposes these days ranging from education, business, and so on, one major area that focuses on individual interaction and communication is online forums. An online forum, or message board, is an online discussion site where people can hold conversations in the form of posted messages. They differ from chat rooms in that, messages are at least temporarily archived. Also, depending on the access level of a user and/or the forum set-up, a posted message might need to be approved by a moderator before it becomes visible. Since information and privacy are very vital as it involves some secrets, strategies, or ideas, there has been a need to protect information from being violated or exposed. This introduces us to the need for a secured online forum, Luke et al. (2003) define Security as the degree of protection against danger, damage, loss, and criminal activity. Security is a form of protection structures and processes that provide or improve security as a condition, here security mechanisms, policies, and privileges can be enforced. With this, private posts can be enhanced and regulations can be applied. In other words, will we design a secure student online forum.

This present era has been termed to be an information age, an age where the demand for information has dramatically increased, the internet has been the most useful place for getting information nowadays, the use of search engines is one of the most useful, the internet is not just used for getting information but for also socializing and exchanging ideas and information, this has led to the development of several software and applications, ranging from the development of online communities and interactive applications. Some of these communities and interactive

applications are included with live chat, instant messaging, forums and online calls. Information is surfed at every possible place, people are interested in sharing and obtaining feedback on their research or who are interested in studying online communities of practice. In a case of a learning community, there are ways in which the community can leverage learning; one of such way is an online forum which is our area of focus.

Sylvia c. (2007) explains, an online forum is a type of interactive website for holding discussions and posting user-generated content, usually each conversation has its own screen, with the original posting at the top, and responses listed in chronological order below. A sense of virtual community often develops around forums that have regular users; it is an instance of the interactive web. Forums differ from chat rooms and instant messaging because forum participants do not have to be online at the same time, they suit short posts, which request a response from others. This online forum can enhance campus-based activities; opportunities to support existing campus-based activities will be explored. For example, faculty learning communities and workshop that are supported through the learning could be supported and promoted through the forum, exchange of expertise and services with other forums.

Luke et al. (2003) explains, one good way to get users to return to your site is to offer Web forum, these can be used for purposes as varied as philosophical discussion groups and product technical support. Web forums are sometimes also called discussion board or threaded discussion groups, the idea of a forum is that people can post articles or question to them and others can read and reply to their questions. Each topic in a forum is usually called thread. Over the years number of reported security breaches has increased, intrusions and attack have become more and more sophisticated and are very common nowadays, since information and privacy are very vital as it involves some secrets, strategies or ideas, there has been need to protect information from being violated or exposed. This introduces us to the need for a secured online forum, where security mechanisms, policies and privileges can be enforced. With this, private posts can be enhanced and regulations can be applied. However, in online forum information and ideas can be shared, individuals who share in an interest in education research and practice can dialogue across disciplines, geographical borders, levels of expertise, and educational sectors. In other words, new threads of discussion by posting articles can be started, viewing articles that have been posted, viewing the threads of conversation in the forum.

1.2 STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

In recent time the quest for this knowledge has risen drastically, surfing or browsing the web without direction for information is becoming stressful especially using search engines. Also getting information in a campus-based community, especially when carrying out research, it can be stressful and expensive. Due to busy schedules of lecturers, they find it difficult passing information to students, students in turn also find it difficult to interact with them, especially to ask question and get ideas. Setting up a forum is actually quite an interesting problem. We will need some way of storing the articles in a database with author, title, date, and content information. However, the way most threaded discussion software works is that, along with showing you the available articles, it will show you the relationship between articles. That is, you are able to see which articles are replies to other articles (and which article they are following up) and which articles are new topics of discussion.

1.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The project is aimed at designing a social community website for lecturers and students' interaction in the Department of Computer Science. The functionalities are related to normal existing social websites, this entails; quick messaging (student-to-student, student-to-lecturer and lecturer-to-lecturer)

- To protect information from unauthorized users by implementing role-based security.
- To implement a secured web forum for students and lecturers of the Department of Computer Science, University of Abuja.

1.3 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This project is centered on building a student online forum using PHP and SQL technology; it is going to elaborate on how security checks can be enforced to an online forum. I will give a general view of online forum, security, and related research ,especially in area like online communities and interactive web. Also, basic security techniques used in interactive web forums.

1.4 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

An interesting area like this is quite tasking, getting the required technical skill to develop this research is a great limitation. Surfing and searching for material and information online is expensive which makes it a major constrain and limitation in this work. Another constrain is time, due to short time frame some areas relating to this research were not covered.

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This research work will help in enhancing our knowledge about implementing an online forum; it will improve the interaction between lecturers and students. This forum is developed in order to facilitate it users to establish network between one-to-many persons and maintain all people's profile. It will also help to save time and energy when they want to share some kind of information, views, ideas to their group friends without spending so much time for communicating to each other. It provides social communism so that people can interact with each other even both of them so far away from each other.

1.6 DEFINITION OF RELATED TERMS

- **Online community:** it is a virtual community that exists online whose members enables its existence through taking part in membership ritual. Many means are used in social software separately or in combination, including text-based chat rooms and forums that use voice, video text or avatars
- **Online forum:** it is an online discussion site where people can hold conversations in the form of posted messages (Wikipedia 2019).
- **Security:** It is the degree of protection against danger, damage, loss, and criminal activity. Security as a form of protection is structures and processes that provide or improve security as a condition. (Merriam et al 2013).
- **Information:**It is any kind of event that affects the state of a dynamic system
- **Message board:** It is an online discussion site where people can hold conversations in the form of posted messages
- **Database:**It is a system intended to organize, store, and retrieve large amounts of data easily (Wikipedia 2004)
- **Query:** A specific set of instructions for extracting a particular data or information (Lechtenberg et al 2022).
- **Repository:**It is a location where large number of information or data are kept or stored.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

2.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter gives an insight into various studies conducted by outstanding researchers, as well as explained terminologies with regard to the design and implementation of a web-based discussion forum for computer science and engineering students. The chapter also gives a resume of the history and present status of the problem delineated by a concise review of previous studies into closely related problems.

2.2 THE CONCEPT OF A WEB-BASED ONLINE FORUM

Online forums also known as discussion boards or message boards enable users of a website to interact with each other by exchanging tips and discussing topics related to a certain theme. Learning through online forums is an important learning strategy for students to improve their language skills along with others. The use of computer-based online discussion through online forums is evident in the curriculum of many courses throughout the world in universities in Australia, New Zealand, South Korea, the United Kingdom, the United States (Scott & Ryan 2009), and Georgia as well. With the rapid development of computer-mediated communication, online forums have become more involved in classroom settings to promote student critical thinking, knowledge construction and language learning autonomy. There is a need for teachers to encourage students to use new technologies such as online forums to gain more exposure in the language along with many other various disciplines. Asynchronous online discussion forums are some of the simplest computer-mediated communication tools that teachers can easily integrate into their teaching to extend discussions beyond classroom contexts.

2.3 CHARACTERISTICS AND INTEGRATION

Online forums require students to participate; grade student efforts; involve learning teams; structure discussions; have a hand in assignments; use experience in posing questions and scenarios; relate the discussion to course objectives; establish a friendly, open environment; use authentic tasks and topics; emphasize learner-centered instructions ;encourage students to give constructive feedback and suggestions; let students experience, reflect and share the benefit of

using threaded discussion; be sure that instructors facilitate collaboration and knowledge building; encourage dialogue and referencing of other student postings; use humor for motivation; use emoticons to help convey ideas and feelings; provide a social presence, in which students and instructor are able to present themselves as "real people" and communicate with their personality. The online discussion forum allows students to work together on projects in small groups, participate in on-going discussions focused on course content, and to "present" group project products to the rest of the class. All of this is done independent of student location and time of actual participation in the discussion forum. This is coordinated with a separate website for the readings and assignments of an online course. Making weekly participation in the discussion a requirement "institutionalizes" the discussion forum within the course. Weekly discussion topics are coordinated with the web course assigned readings for each week. Students are asked to respond to one or to pen-ended questions designed to elicit discussion about the topics. Requiring students to respond to at least three other student postings initiates a round of discussion among the participants. Each student's posting is listed in the forum under the weekly topic. Student group projects are on-going across 14 weeks of a 15-week semester. Students assign themselves to a topic by posting their name and email addresses and stating what subtopic they are interested in doing research on. Group size is usually limited to 6-10 students for ease of communication. Students may exclusively use the work area set aside for their topic in the discussion forum or they may correspond using email or chat rooms.

All postings within the large group are public and archived so that whole transcripts can be reviewed as needed and readily accessible to all participants. This written record constitutes a body of knowledge collectively written by participants in the course. Group project work can be public or sheltered by password assignment. Participation in the virtual conference demands that students become actively engaged with the course content and through the interaction with their peers, negotiate the meanings of the content. They construct knowledge through the shared experiences that each participant brings to the collaborative discussions. The online web courses about teaching offer deeper perspectives and opportunities to learn because the participants are teachers from school districts around the state and other states. This is not a narrowing of perspectives, but a broadening of the knowledge base as experiences are shared and compared relative to teaching issues. This particular use of the discussion forum, to negotiate and construct knowledge, is an example of using the technology as a cognitive tool and not simply as another kind of blackboard

or one-way communication method. Cognitive tools and environments stimulate cognitive learning strategies and critical thinking (Jonassen, 1998). Students engaged with course content in discussions and group work with other students engage in generative processing of information. Students draw upon their own experiences and interpretations and share these with the group discussion. They draw on their own teacher stories to relate to the course content. They read other student responses and interpretations and compare these with their own thoughts. This involves the processes of reflection and the construction and reconstruction of domains of knowledge. It is a negotiated interpretation of knowledge with student ownership. The learning is deeper and more long lasting and students refine their thinking and their voice. The discussion forum environment evens the playing field of opportunity and accessibility. Those students who have a reflective style that does not lend itself to quick, off the hip questions or comments now have time to contribute their well thought out responses. Connections that few have time to make in the stream of classroom discourse now stand out in a discussion forum flow of asynchronous discussion. Those students who migrate to the back of classrooms suddenly find that in the virtual environment their voice is not only solicited, but it is required and they are discovering that they can interact with the content of the course and their peers. Group work within this environment imparts a shared sense of purpose and develops a group identity with a sense of interdependence and belonging. The initiation of these tasks can be perceived as exceptionally difficult for students who are not familiar with the concept in a web-based environment. The tasks must be structured with clear instructions and expectations. The public display of group work products in the discussion forum through the use of graphics, Power Point displays, or links to web sites maximizes the learning potential for the whole class and provides a model for students to use in future work. Students are never anonymous as their name is posted with their comments. They develop an identity online as well as a voice as they tell their stories and mutually construct understandings around the course content.

The discussion forum makes active participation by all students the price of citizenship within this learning community. The asynchronous environment assures that there is time enough for all to respond. Hartman, et al. (1996) found that computer-mediated communication did not just redistribute shares of a constant pie (communication time), it actually increased the size of the pie. Communication is among all participants, including the instructor and it is accessible at all times.

2.4 BENEFITS OF ONLINE FORUMS

Online forums provide many benefits to students and teachers. Students are found to be in favor of the self-paced, self-regulated feature of asynchronous discussions compared to face-to-face discussions. On the other hand, online forums create a discussion environment. Everything that gets posted gets read over and over again. Online forums rarely turn into heated arguments as people are given time to research and consider their comments before replying. This in turn, makes high-quality discussion. Smith (2001) points out that well-structured and appropriately facilitated online discussion can provide a learning environment that allows the immediate application of new information to learners' personal and professional lives. Besides, online forums are more flexible compared to face to face communication as they provide time to reflect and think and allow both introverted and extroverted students to be involved in online discussions. By participating in online forums, access to knowledge is free; forum members could willingly share their wealth of knowledge and experience with other members. In return, every member of the forum can benefit from this infusion of free knowledge.

Here are some potential benefits of regular online forum participation according to Pavlina (2005): Intellectual exchange; learning new ideas and refining old ones; enjoying community membership; influencing the forum's evolution; contributing to others; making new friends and contacts; new business leads; keeping up with current events; learning about new opportunities.

There has been evidence that the messages composed by students in online forums include longer solutions for problem-solving, and consist of deeper reflections compared to face-to-face discussions. Researchers have found that students can take more time to read, craft, reflect on their responses, and find relevant information when composing messages in such an environment (O'Neill et al. 2006). Online discussions build a motivating social practice of current generation students, who use technology to contact friends family throughout the day. In online forums, students develop their autonomy in language learning.

Each participant is given more authority to shape or lead the discussion in the direction they prefer, while teachers may have relatively less control over the learning interactions.

A well-structured online discussion forum can provide students with extensive practice in writing. The online forum allows opportunities for the facilitation of curricular objectives via modern technology. Online discussion forums provide an authenticity in writing and therefore serve as a

meaningful supplement to the writing curriculum. The implementation of the online forum appears to provide reinforcement tasks to enable students to practice their writing. Besides that, the online forum also facilitates collaborative learning. Students could share their ideas and opinions in order to produce better quality writing as compared to if the tasks were to be completed independently. Schuetze (2010) conducted a research in the University of Victoria Canada and the University of Kiel in Germany. The study showed that most students of both universities felt comfortable writing online and they wrote more than ever before. They used the forum more actively than in a face-to-face classroom or chat. In turn, some students also mentioned that they liked to read what other students posted in online forums. In a study among twenty-five Chinese and Kiwi learners, Gerbric (2005) encountered that online forums provide opportunities specifically for particular groups of students. Chinese students found the virtual and text-based nature of the medium allowed them to enter discussions more easily and they felt more comfortable with their written responses compared to face-to-face discussions.

A number of studies have found that online forums are beneficial in developing communication skills. The greatest potential for effective use of online communication as a learning tool is when the students are 'at a distance' from the school and their teachers.

Holmes (2004) acknowledged a period of increased communication between online participants of his study after 10 days of interaction on online forum and asserted that input from teachers or instructors during this period led to maximized learning opportunities.

Scott and Ryan (2009) in their study discovered that online members become more engaged in discussions and interacted effectively when they were set appropriate tasks. For example, a complex task that requires research and discussion is more suitable for small groups to work on collaboratively. When students are given problems related to their prior experience, the discussions show higher levels of interaction, and the participants show more passion for the topic.

Through online forums, teachers are able to document the growth of their students' ability to support a point in their messages. Students improved their ability to respond to a classmate and to make a point supported with evidence.

Online forums are a good way of communicating, especially when the teacher or lecturer is unavailable. It is also a good way to communicate with everyone as it creates a good communication between students and school. Students are more comfortable and less aggressive when participating in online forums. Online forums also offered more equal opportunities for

group members to voice their opinions; they demonstrate very high levels of interaction among group members. Online forums are regarded as a social interaction that reduces students' reliance on the face-to-face discussions.

2.5 CHALLENGES OF IMPLEMENTING ONLINE WEB BASED DISCUSSION FORUMS

Because of the limited opportunities for face-to-face interactions between an instructor and their students, distance education has brought many new challenges to the teaching and learning process. Effective curriculum design is hindered by the lack of understanding of the characteristics, attitudes, and needs of the students in these courses (Williams, 2006). At the same time, the faculty needs to develop skills in helping students adjust to the unique features of distance education. However, the lack of adequate training may prevent them from fully participating in the distance education practices, especially considering that they have to spend twice as much time in preparing and delivering an online course as compared to a traditional course. Distance learning students desire content and motivational support beyond course materials and are limited in their success without it (Williams, 2006). Collaborative learning is necessary in building one's own cognitive process. To promote learner-centered education, the American Psychological Association (APA) designed a document -- Learner-Centered Psychological Principles -- to provide a guideline of the factors affecting learning in the 1990s (APA Work Group of the Board of Educational Affairs, 1997). It includes 14 principles which are grouped into four domains: cognitive and metacognitive factors, motivational and affective factors, developmental and social factors, and individual differences factors. Principle 11 relates closely with student interaction issues under the developmental and social factors. It states that learning is influenced by social interactions, interpersonal relations, and communication with others.

Besides active communication, interaction, online presence, and moderated discussions, the formation of an online community is one of the key elements for high-quality online education. Fostering interactivity in an online community is the main indicator of success in online courses (Bender, 2003).

Outcome of traditional education and distance education are the same, only if one selects the appropriate teaching material and method, including student-to-student interaction and timely teacher-to-student feedback. In general, the collaborative learning culture promoted by the cognitive apprenticeship theory can be applied into all the situations of the teaching and learning processes. However, because of its unique application for the distance education field and the

urgent needs of such theories in the field, the cognitive apprenticeship theory is very helpful in planning distance learning courses.

The implementation of a constructivist approach to learning and teaching that emphasises the “social” construction of knowledge causes some problems for both the online learner and online teacher. Some learners may prefer to work independently so group projects, or the requirement to participate in online discussion forums at a particular period of time in a course may not suit all approaches to learning.

The level of learner engagement with communication features is both a reflection of the design of the online course, and the ability of teachers to engage the learners in dialogue.

It indicates that online interaction between course participants is a critical feature of online teaching. The emphasis placed on social interaction in a constructivist context and the opportunities for interaction provided by technology support the importance of collaboration and group knowledge construction in an online context. In the online classroom, it is the relationships and interactions among people through which knowledge is primarily generated.

Operating in the online environment means that bodily differences and social values attached to visible differences are invisible and irrelevant - teachers and learners online construct themselves through text in the discussion forums, for example (distinctions of gender, ethnicity, body shape or impairment, accent or speech styles ‘don’t matter’ – visual cues of difference are missing) and the challenge is to know more about online sociality and the ‘special circumstances’ of learners.

Using grades to reward participation requires careful thought, as meaningless postings do not equate to quality learning outcomes. Clearly defined expectations in terms of levels of participation and assessment requirements are essential.

2.6 ADMIN ROLES IN WEB-BASED SITE

Course leaders have the opportunity with the online environment to adapt, modify and change whole sections of the course, or ways previously planned to proceed, to engage with content, to assess – according to the students’ needs, interests, expectations, contexts and prior learning’s, so long as the Course Specification (objectives, etc.) continue to be met.

Online means being able to truly take account of what students want, re-shaping the environment to make the most of students’ collective experience and expertise, mobilizing them to construct knowledge for their own purposes.

Online instructors rated the following as the top four techniques for keeping asynchronous online discussion on topic:

- carefully design questions that specifically elicit on-topic discussion,
- provide guidelines to help online learners prepare on-topic responses,
- reword the original question when responses are going in the wrong direction, and
- provide discussion summary on a regular basis.

From the growing use of online forums for education, we see that they can operate well — with specific questions getting resolved quickly, and open-ended discussion questions receiving a strong flow of contributions. But they can also operate poorly, with little student participation and questions that go unanswered for long periods of time. An instructor would like to make use of an online forum so as to promote better outcomes. How can an instructor use her own behavior to incentivize higher student participation? For example, if the instructor actively appears on the site, does this tend to increase student participation (because they are hoping to get the instructor’s approval) or decrease it (because they assume that the instructor will answer the questions herself)? Is there an optimal way to trade off these two forces, and how does the best outcome the instructor can elicit through her behavior depend on the size of the class — as the class size becomes large, can the instructor step back and let the class do most of the work on the forum? While such questions appear at the heart of discussions about best practices in these forums (Andresen 2009), there has so far not been a formal way of reasoning about them.

In a study that asks the question of what role an instructor should undertake in an asynchronous discussion forum (sage, guide, or ghost), Andersen (2009) found that it depends on what the instructor wishes to accomplish. Learner ratings of a course will show that an instructor is more enthusiastic and expert if s/he increases his/her postings. structure that contributes significantly to a discussion tends to decrease the length of discussions (this does not necessarily decrease the quality of the discussion, however) as well as their frequency. What appears to be occurring in this situation is that the instructor can decrease learner-learner interaction because the learners begin to rely on the instructor to answer questions, becoming the expert or sage to ‘settle’ debates.

The role of the instructor in online discussion forums is a key one in many forms of online education. However, (Mazzolini et al, 2005) argue that without face-to-face feedback, it is not easy for instructors to gauge the “health” of their discussion forums, especially when dealing with

distance education students, and it can also be difficult for coordinators of online programs to judge when their instructors are doing a good job in supporting their students-learning online.

The coordinators of online programs are likely to judge forums intuitively and assume that forums containing large numbers of student postings are best. As a consequence, they are likely to encourage their instructors to “jump in” often, by making frequent postings and starting new discussion threads in order to encourage students to post. If coordinators aim to achieve positive responses for issues such as instructor enthusiasm and expertise on university evaluation surveys, then our experience suggests that coordinators should encourage their instructors to post often, even if the student posting rate does go down in the process. Obviously, there is a balance to be achieved here. Instructors posted approximately half their postings during each forum and half at the end, which is compatible with the instructor survey. Instructors who tend to post most towards or at the end of forums scored particularly highly for enthusiasm and expertise on university evaluation surveys, but as these were the instructors who also tended to post the most overall, this was not surprising. The instructors tended to post questions, answers or a mixture of both, had very little effect on students - responses to the surveys, except that students did seem to regard instructors who answered lots of questions as more enthusiastic, and they did not appreciate it when instructors mainly posted “housekeeping” type postings rather than engaging actively in the online discussions.

2.6 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Williams (2006) applies the institutional theory to higher education institutions and concludes that six basic components underly the institutions’ capacity of offering distance education courses. The six basic components are administrative commitment (allocating resources), Online student support services (registration, advising, providing access), Fulltime online coordinator (assisting course development and online teaching issues), Internal/External financial and technology resources (computers, online course management system), Online professional development (developing faculty online knowledge), and Adequate faculty participation (enough innovators supporting online education). Teachers are experiencing change in terms of their teaching philosophies, their relationships with learners, and their work patterns and activities. The physical space defined by a classroom has been replaced by a virtual space defined by a learning management system. Teachers’ roles have changed from being the “experts” in their field to being facilitators of learning. They are reasonably comfortable with the notion that they combine this

role with another one that defines them as learning partners. This is a situation that not only allows but also encourages other members of the group to assume leadership by enabling participants' opportunities to change the course direction, share resources or assist the group by proposing initiatives. Much progress is being made in getting the best out of the online environment. Nevertheless, it is pointed out that many of the difficulties that online teachers continue to raise focus on the tensions between teaching philosophies, learner expectations and traditional organizational mindsets. While the experienced teachers are well aware of the importance of shared understandings, there is also the acknowledgement that the rapid pace of change in the information and communication technologies requires a great deal of flexibility and adaptability by both teachers and learners.

CHAPTER THREE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter describes in detail the system design methodology. It focuses on the system structure and interactions. The proposed system is a web base forum system. The propose system which will be deploy on the on the web is aimed at providing a system which will create a discussion forum where users can create various topics, reply topics and moderate topics by the administrator of the site or super moderators. This chapter begins by examining the Systems Requirement Specification (SRS) document which is majorly focused on only the functional requirements to be provided by the system. It proceeds to the system design which consists of the logic design. The logic design consists of various user interfaces and the chapter also explains the system design using UML diagrams.(Christy et al., 2001).

3.2 SYSTEM REQUIREMENT SPECIFICATION

The system requirement specification is a structured document that collects information that encompasses the requirements of a system. This section would focus mainly on the functional requirements of the proposed system and these include:

- The system should be able to validate all user input and respond to exceptions appropriately.
- The system should enforce the policy of non-multiple users of an account using standard authentication processes.
- The system should allow the admin to create and maintain category and topic details.
- The system should allow for secure financial transactions as related to admin expenses.
- The system should be able to track insecure penetrations and prevent unauthorized intrusions.
- The system should also allow users to maintain an online profile.

3.2 SYSTEM DESIGN

This section explains the design methodology, data and modules for the proposed system. The system design incorporates both UML diagrams and user interface designs.

3.2.1 logical design

The logical design of the system is concerned with the underlying logic of the proposed system which would be abstracted from the various interfaces of the system. The interfaces discussed would be the input design, output design, and menu design.

3.2.2 Input design

This section includes the various input design interfaces in the system. The input design interfaces to be considered would be the login form interface, Create Topic, Create Category and Create an account interfaces.

LOGIN WINDOW

The image shows a login window with a white background and a black border. On the left side, there are two labels: "User Name:" and "Password:". To the right of "User Name:" is a long, empty rectangular text input field. To the right of "Password:" is a shorter, empty rectangular text input field. Below the password field is another empty rectangular text input field. At the bottom left of the window, there is a rectangular button with the text "Login Now" inside it.

Figure 3.1: Login Interface (Simons, 2000).

The Login interface allows authorize personnel to login into the system to make change and obtain appropriate results. The actual form contains more detailed information as seen in the application.

Create Topic

Create a Topic	
Subject:	<input type="text"/>
Category:	<input type="text" value="IV"/>
Message:	<input type="text"/>
<input type="button" value="Create Topic"/>	

Figure 3.2: Create Topic Interface (Admin)

Create Category

Create a Category	
Category Name:	<input type="text"/>
Category description	<input type="text"/>
<input type="button" value="Add Category"/>	

Figure 3.3: Create Category Interface

CREATE AN ACCOUNT

Sign up	
Username:	<input type="text"/>
Password:	<input type="password"/>
Password again:	<input type="password"/>
Email:	<input type="text"/>
<input type="button" value="Add category"/>	

Figure 3.4: Create Account Interface (User)

3.2.3 OUTPUT DESIGN

This section describes the various output of the system to the user. The format of output for the system is majorly text. The output that would be discussed would be the

3.2.4 MENU DESIGN

The menu design describes the various paths or menus available to the user of the system. The menu design below shows the major options provided for a user:

View Category

View Category

S/N	Category	Date Created
1	-----	-----
2	--	-----
3	-----	-----
4	-----	-----

Figure 3.5: View Category Window (Admin)

View Forum Topic

Forum Name
Creator Name:
Date Created:
Reply
<div style="border: 1px solid black; height: 100px; width: 100%;"></div>
<div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; padding: 5px;">Submit Reply</div>

Figure 3.6: View Forum Topic Window

Welcome Screen

Home	Create Topic	Create: Category	Sign in	Create Account
------	--------------	------------------	---------	----------------

Figure 3.7: Welcome Screen Window

3.2.5 Use case diagram

The use case diagram is a UML diagram that shows the users of a system and the various interactions that exists between the user and the system.

Figure 3.8: Use Case Diagram (User and Admin)

Logout

3.3 STRUCTURE OF DATABASE DESIGN

The proposed system makes use of a relational database to store and maintain records. This database will consist of four (4) relational tables discussed below:

Categories Table

Field	Data type	Description
Cat-id	Int (8)	Category id
Cat- name	Varchar(255)	Category name
Cat- description	Varchar(255)	Contain Category description

Post Table

Field	Data type	
Post id	Int(8)	Post ID
Post-content	text	Post Content
Post-date	Date/ time	Post date
Post-topic	Int(8)	Post topic
Post-by	Int(8)	Post by WHO

Topic Table

Field	Data type	Description
Topic-id	Int (8)	Topic id
Topic- subject	Varchar (255)	Topic subject
Topic- date	Date time	Topic Date
Topic-cat	Int (8)	Topic category
Topic-by	Int (8)	Topic post by who

User Table

Field	Data type	Description
User-id	Int (18)	User ID
User- name	Varchar (255)	User name
User-pass	Varchar (255)	User password
User- email	Varchar (255)	User Email
User- date	Date time	User Date
User-level	Int (8)	User access level

CHAPTER FOUR

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter focuses on the implementation of the system. The features of the implementation languages used in this research- PHP and MYSQL will be discussed extensively. The system testing strategies, the target computer requirements as well as the software maintenance issues that would arise in the system would be discussed also.

4.2 FEATURES OF IMPLEMENTATION LANGUAGES

The programming languages used in the implementation of this project are PHP (Hypertext Preprocessor) and MYSQL programming languages. PHP is a general-purpose server-side scripting language originally designed for web development to produce dynamic web pages. It has also evolved to include a command line interface capability and can be used in stand-alone graphical applications.

The following features make PHP a preferred implementation language for this project:

- PHP has its root in C and C++. PHP syntax is most similar to C and C++ language syntax, so programmers find it easy to learn and manipulate.
- PHP can run on both UNIX and windows. Hence it is compatible across various operating systems.
- PHP has powerful output buffering that further increases over the output flow. PHP internally rearranges the buffer so that the header comes before the content.
- PHP is platform independent: this is because it is parsed by the web browser hence compatibility issues do not arise when code written in PHP is ported to a different platform.
- PHP can be used with a large number of relational database management systems, runs on all of the most popular web servers and is available to many different operating systems.
- PHP is fully an object-oriented programming language and its platform independence and speed on LINUX servers help to build large and complex web applications.
- PHP has also attracted the development of many frameworks that provide building blocks and design structure to promote Rapid Application Development (RAD).

Some of these include cake PHP, code igniter, Yii framework and Zend framework.

- PHP IDS add security to any PHP application to defend against intrusion. PHPIDS detects cross-site scripting (XSS), SQL injection, header injection, directory traversal, remote file execution, local file execution and Denial of Service (DOS).

MYSQL is a relational database management system written in C and C++, that runs as a server providing multi user access to a number of databases. MYSQL is used basically to create a relational database structure on a server in order to store data or automate procedures. The following features make MYSQL also a preferred implementation language in this research:

- MYSQL is written in C and C++ and tested with a broad range of different compilers. It also functions on different platforms.
- It uses multi-layered server design with independent modules.
- It is designed to be fully multi-threaded using kernel threads to easily use multiple CPUs if they are available.
- It is a server/client system. The database server (MYSQL) and the arbitrary many clients (application programs) which communicates with the server to query data and save changes.
- MYSQL is designed to make it relatively easy to add other storage engines. This is useful if you want to provide an SQL interface for an in-house database.
- It provides transactional and non-transactional storage engines, uses very fast B-tree disk tables with index compression and a fast thread-base memory allocation system.
- It executes very fast joins using an optimized nested loop join; implements in-memory hash tables which are used as temporary tables.
- It implements SQL functions using a highly optimized class library that should be as fast as possible.
- It provides the server as a separate program for use in a client/server networked environment and as a library that can be embedded (linked) into stand-alone applications. Such applications can be used in isolation or in environments where no network is available.

4.3 SYSTEM TESTING STRATEGIES

This section is concerned with testing and debugging the programs and general processes involved in achieving the objectives of the system requirement. System testing is conducted on a complete integrated system to evaluate the system's compliance with its specified requirements. System testing falls within the scope of black box testing and as such should require no knowledge of the inner design of the code or logic. During system testing, the focus is on the software design, behavior, and even the believed expectations of the customer. So, we can also refer to the system testing phase as the investigatory testing phase of the software development life cycle. The system testing strategies used in this system include the unit test and integration test.

4.3.1 Unit test

The primary goal of unit testing is to take the smallest piece of testable software in the application, isolate it from the remainder of the code and determine whether it behaves exactly as it is expected to behave. Each unit is tested separately before integrating them into modules to test the interfaces between modules. Unit testing has proven its value in that a large percentage of defects are identified during its use. The most common approach to unit testing requires drivers and stubs to be written. The driver simulates a calling unit and the stub simulates a called unit. The investment of developer time in this activity sometimes results in demoting unit testing to a lower level of priority and that is almost always a mistake. Even though the drivers and stubs cost time and money, unit testing provides some undeniable advantages. It allows for automation of the testing process and reduces difficulties in discovering errors contained in complex pieces of the application. During the unit testing of the application, errors uncovered by the researcher were rectified and the result was satisfactory.

4.3.2 Integration testing

Integration testing is a logical extension of unit testing. In its simplest form, the units that have already been tested are combined into a component and the interface between them is tested. A component, in this sense, refers to an integrated aggregate of more than one unit. In a realistic scenario, many units are combined into components, which are in turn aggregated into even larger parts of the program. The idea is to test the combination of pieces and eventually expand the process to test your modules with those of other groups. Integration testing can be done in a variety

of ways which include the top-down approach, the bottom-up approach, and the umbrella approach. In the integration testing of the software, satisfactory results were obtained from the test using the bottom-up approach.

4.4 TARGET COMPUTER SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

This section considers the requirements that must be met by the target system to enable the developed software application function as required. The target computer system requirement will be discussed in the area of software and hardware requirements.

Component	Requirement
Operating system	Windows 2000, XP, Vista
Memory	128MB or higher
Database	MySQL 5
Web server	WAMP server

Table 4.1: Software requirement for target computer system

Component	Requirement
RAM	256MB of RAM
Hard disk	10GB of hard disk space
Processor	333Hz or higher

Table 4.2: Hardware requirements for target computer system

4.5 SOFTWARE MAINTENANCE ISSUES

This section focuses on software maintenance issues. Software maintenance is the modification of a software product after delivery to correct faults, improve performance or other product attributes or to adapt the product to a new or changing environment. It also serves as an opportunity to improve the performance of the software to suit the needs of the users if it becomes necessary for the user requirements to be improved upon or changed. Maintenance would be seen in three areas in this research; corrective maintenance, preventive maintenance and adaptive maintenance.

4.5.1 Corrective maintenance

Corrective maintenance is a maintenance task performed to identify, isolate and rectify a fault so that the failed system can be restored to an operational condition within the tolerances or limits established for in-service operations. Necessary corrections in the form of removal, modification or addition of program modules should be permitted by the software to allow for optimal use of the application.

4.5.2 Preventive maintenance

This is a schedule of planned maintenance actions aimed at the prevention of breakdowns and failures. The primary goal of preventive maintenance is to prevent the failure of software before it actually occurs. It is designed to preserve and enhance software reliability by replacing error-prone components before they actually fail. Recent technological advances in tools for inspection and diagnosis have enabled more accurate and effective software maintenance. Measures like regular diagnosis, database backups, and creating system mirrors preserve the integrity of information stored in the application. If these are strictly followed, limited instances of such occurrences would be noticed in the use of the software application.

4.5.3 Adaptive maintenance

This involves enhancing the system by adding features, capabilities, and functions in response to new technology, upgrades, new requirements, or new problems. Since the environment in which the application would be running is dynamic, it should be made to suit whatever requirements may change in the long run.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.0 INTRODUCTION

This chapter focuses on summary, conclusion and recommendations. Here, the entire summary of the research from the problem stage to the implementation stage, the relevant conclusion and recommendations are discussed.

5.1 SUMMARY

The world is fast becoming a global village due to the effect of globalization and rapid growth in technology. This has enabled information sharing among various people of the world, thereby solving basic societal problems and bringing about rapid development. The study designs and implements a web-based forum where computer science and computer engineering students of a particular university, or various universities in Nigeria and the world at large can come together and interact online. Various rooms/categories such as programming, web development, networking, computer repairs/maintenance, android/IOS discussions, phone and technology in general can be integrated into this online forum. Faced with the challenges many computer sciences and engineering students face when trying to execute some of their projects, the researcher deem it fit to create a social platform where students can register, log in, ask IT questions and get quality answers from users and admin, create numerous computer and ICT related topics to inform others, and get others to read their thoughts and projects and reply or like their post. Concerning methodology, the system was created using PHP and MySQL. The aim of the system is to create a discussion forum where users can create various topics, reply topics and moderate topics by the administrator of the site or super moderators.

5.2 CONCLUSION

A web-based forum system is a system that is computerized to provide an optimal discussion forum where implemented. The incorporation of categories and topics for separate different category where related make it outstanding. The system model categories as created by the admin and different topics respectively, users are given the access to comment on multiple topics of interest.

5.3 RECOMMENDATION

Having designed, tested and implemented the new system, the following must be put in place to fully achieve the objective of which the software is designed.

- Maintenance: The system needs to be maintained. This implies that any fault detected should be reported to the programmer for correction at any point in time.
- Internet Connection: The system needs to be connected to the internet before the user can access the features of the software online else it can be deployed offline using a remote server(local server: WAMP, XAMP, MANP e.t.c).
- Research: More research should be conducted on the topic to assess it effectively.

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APPENDIX 1

Home Page

<style>

```
.carousel-item>img{
```

```
    object-fit:fill !important;
```

```
}
```

```
#carouselExampleControls .carousel-inner{
```

```
    height:280px !important;
```

```
}
```

```
#search-field .form-control.rounded-pill{
```

```
    border-top-right-radius:0 !important;
```

```
    border-bottom-right-radius:0 !important;
```

```
    border-right:none !important
```

```
}
```

```
#search-field .form-control:focus{
```

```
    box-shadow:none !important;
```

```
}
```

```
#search-field .form-control:focus + .input-group-append .input-group-text{
```

```
    border-color: #86b7fe !important
```

```
}
```

```
#search-field .input-group-text.rounded-pill{
```

```
    border-top-left-radius:0 !important;
```

```

border-bottom-left-radius:0 !important;

border-right:left !important
}

.post-item{

transition:all .2s ease-in-out;

}

.post-item:hover{

transform:scale(1.02);

}

</style>

<section class="py-3">

<div class="container">

<div class="row">

<div class="col-md-12">

<div id="carouselExampleControls" class="carousel slide bg-dark" data-
ride="carousel">

<div class="carousel-inner">

<?php

$upload_path = "uploads/banner";

if(is_dir(base_app.$upload_path)):

$file= scandir(base_app.$upload_path);

$_i = 0;

foreach($file as $img):

```

```

        if(in_array($img,array('!','..')))
            continue;

        $_i++;

    ?>
    <div class="carousel-item h-100 <?php echo $_i == 1 ? "active" : " ?>">

        ">

    </div>

<?php endforeach; ?>

<?php endif; ?>

</div>

        <button class="carousel-control-prev" type="button" data-
target="#carouselExampleControls" data-slide="prev">

        <span class="carousel-control-prev-icon" aria-hidden="true"></span>

        <span class="visually-hidden">Previous</span>

    </button>

        <button class="carousel-control-next" type="button" data-
target="#carouselExampleControls" data-slide="next">

        <span class="carousel-control-next-icon" aria-hidden="true"></span>

        <span class="visually-hidden">Next</span>

    </button>

</div>

```

```

    </div>
</div>
<div class="row justify-content-center my-4">
    <div class="col-lg-6 col-md-8 col-sm-12 col-xs-12">
        <div class="input-group input-group-lg" id="search-field">
            <input type="search" class="form-control form-control-lg rounded-pill" aria-
label="Search Post Input" id="search" placeholder="Search post here">
            <div class="input-group-append">
                <span class="input-group-text rounded-pill bg-transparent"><i class="fa fa-
search"></i></span>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
<div class="row row-cols-xl-4 row-cols-md-3 row-cols-sm-1 gx-2 gy-2">
    <?php
        $posts = $conn->query("SELECT p.*, c.name as `category` FROM `post_list` p inner join
category_list c on p.category_id = c.id where p.status = 1 and p.`delete_flag` = 0 order by
abs(unix_timestamp(p.date_created)) desc");
        while($row = $posts->fetch_assoc()):
            ?>
            <div class="col post-item">

```

```

    <a href="/?p=posts/view_post&id=<?= $row['id'] ?>" class="card rounded-0 shadow
text-decoration-none text-reset">

    <div class="card-body">

        <div class="mb-2 text-right">

            <small class="badge badge-light border text-dark rounded-pill px-3"><i
class="far fa-circle"></i> <?= $row['category'] ?></small>

        </div>

        <h3 class="card-title w-100 font-weight-bold"><?= $row['title'] ?></h3>

            <div class="card-text truncate-3 text-muted text-sm"><?=
strip_tags($row['content']) ?></div>

            <div class="mb-2 text-right">

                <small class="text-muted"><i><?= date("Y-m-d h:i A",
strtotime($row['date_created'])) ?></i></small>

            </div>

        </div>

    </a>

</div>

<?php endwhile; ?>

</div>

</div>

</section>

<script>

$(function(){

```

```

$( '#search' ).on( 'input', function() {
    var _search = $( this ).val().toLowerCase()

    $( '.post-item' ).each( function() {
        var _text = $( this ).text().toLowerCase()
        _text = _text.trim()

        if( _text.includes( _search ) === false ) {
            $( this ).toggle( false )
        } else {
            $( this ).toggle( true )
        }
    } )
} )
} )
</script>

```

Login Page

```

<?php require_once( './config.php' ) ?>
<?php require_once( 'inc/sess_auth.php' ) ?>
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en" class="" style="height: auto;">
<?php require_once( 'inc/header.php' ) ?>
<body class="hold-transition login-page">
<script>
    start_loader()

```

```

</script>
<style>
  body{
    background-image: url("<?php echo validate_image($_settings->info('cover')) ?>");
    background-size:cover;
    background-repeat:no-repeat;
    backdrop-filter: contrast(1);
  }
  #page-title{
    text-shadow: 6px 4px 7px black;
    font-size: 3.5em;
    color: #fff4f4 !important;
    background: #8080801c;
  }
</style>
  <h1 class="text-center text-white px-4 py-5" id="page-title"><b><?php echo $_settings-
>info('name') ?></b></h1>
<div class="login-box">
  <!-- /.login-logo -->
  <div class="card card-navy my-2">
    <div class="card-body">
      <p class="login-box-msg">Please enter your credentials</p>
      <form id="ulogin-form" action="" method="post">

```

```

<div class="input-group mb-3">
    <input type="text" class="form-control" name="username" autofocus
placeholder="Username">
    <div class="input-group-append">
        <div class="input-group-text">
            <span class="fas fa-user"></span>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
<div class="input-group mb-3">
    <input type="password" class="form-control" name="password" placeholder="Password">
    <div class="input-group-append">
        <div class="input-group-text">
            <span class="fas fa-lock"></span>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
<div class="row">
    <div class="col-8">
        <a href="<?php echo base_url ?>">Go to Website</a>
    </div>
    <!-- /.col -->
    <div class="col-4">

```

```
<button type="submit" class="btn btn-primary btn-block">Sign In</button>
</div>
<div class="col-12 text-center">
  <a href="<?php echo base_url ?>register.php">Create an Account</a>
</div>
<!-- /.col -->
</div>
</form>
<!-- /.social-auth-links -->

<!-- <p class="mb-1">
  <a href="forgot-password.html">I forgot my password</a>
</p> -->

</div>
<!-- /.card-body -->
</div>
<!-- /.card -->
</div>
<!-- /.login-box -->

<!-- jQuery -->
<script src="plugins/jquery/jquery.min.js"></script>
```

```

<!-- Bootstrap 4 -->

<script src="plugins/bootstrap/js/bootstrap.bundle.min.js"></script>

<!-- AdminLTE App -->

<script src="dist/js/adminlte.min.js"></script>

<script>

$(document).ready(function(){

    end_loader();

    $('#login-form').submit(function(e){

        e.preventDefault()

        var _this = $(this)

        var el = $('<div>')

        el.addClass('alert alert-danger err_msg')

        el.hide()

        $('err_msg').remove()

        if($('#password').val() != $('#cpassword').val()){

            el.text('Password does not match')

            _this.prepend(el)

            el.show('slow')

            $('html, body').scrollTop(0)

            return false;

        }

    }

}

```

```

if(_this[0].checkValidity() == false){
    _this[0].reportValidity();
    return false;
}
start_loader()
$.ajax({
    url:_base_url_"classes/Login.php?f=login_user",
    method:'POST',
    type:'POST',
    data:new FormData($(this)[0]),
    dataType:'json',
    cache:false,
    processData:false,
    contentType: false,
    error:err=>{
        console.log(err)
        alert('An error occurred')
        end_loader()
    },
    success:function(resp){
        if(resp.status == 'success'){
            location.href = ('/')
        }else if (!!resp.msg){

```

```

        el.html(resp.msg)

        el.show('slow')

        _this.prepend(el)

        $('html, body').scrollTop(0)

    }else{

        alert('An error occurred')

        console.log(resp)

    }

    end_loader()

}

})

})

})

</script>

</body>

</html>

```

Registration Page

```

<?php require_once('./config.php') ?>

<!DOCTYPE html>

<html lang="en" class="" style="height: auto;">

<?php require_once('inc/header.php') ?>

<script>

    start_loader()

```

```
</script>
<style>
html, body{
    width:100%;
    height:100% !important;
}
body{
    background-image: url("<?php echo validate_image($_settings->info('cover')) ?>");
    background-size:cover;
    background-repeat:no-repeat;
    backdrop-filter: contrast(1);
    overflow-x:hidden
}
#page-title{
    text-shadow: 6px 4px 7px black;
    font-size: 3.5em;
    color: #fff4f4 !important;
    background: #8080801c;
}
img#cimg{
    height: 5em;
    width: 5em;
    object-fit: cover;
```

```

border-radius: 100% 100%;

}

</style>

<body class="">

  <div class="d-flex flex-column align-items-center justify-content-center h-100 w-100">

    <h1 class="text-center text-white px-4 py-5" id="page-title"><b><?php echo $_settings-
>info('name') ?></b></h1>

  <div class="col-lg-6 col-md-8 col-sm-12 col-xs-12">

    <!-- /.login-logo -->

    <div class="card card-navy my-2 rounded-0">

      <div class="card-header rounded-0">

        <h4 class="card-title">Registration</h4>

      </div>

      <div class="card-body rounded-0">

        <form id="register-form" action="" method="post">

          <input type="hidden" name="id">

          <input type="hidden" name="type" value="2">

          <div class="row">

            <div class="col-lg-6 col-md-6 col-sm-12 col-xs-12">

              <div class="form-group">

                <label for="firstname" class="control-label">First Name</label>

                <input type="text" class="form-control form-control-sm rounded-0" required=""
name="firstname" id="firstname">

```

```

</div>

<div class="form-group">

  <label for="middlename" class="control-label">Middle Name</label>

    <input type="text" class="form-control form-control-sm rounded-0"
name="middlename" id="middlename">

</div>

<div class="form-group">

  <label for="lastname" class="control-label">Last Name</label>

  <input type="text" class="form-control form-control-sm rounded-0" required=""
name="lastname" id="lastname">

</div>

</div>

<div class="col-lg-6 col-md-6 col-sm-12 col-xs-12">

  <div class="form-group">

    <label for="username" class="control-label">Username</label>

    <input type="text" class="form-control form-control-sm rounded-0" required=""
name="username" id="username">

</div>

<div class="form-group">

  <label for="password" class="control-label">Password</label>

  <div class="input-group input-group-sm">

    <input type="password" class="form-control form-control-sm rounded-0"
required="" name="password" id="password">

```

```

        <button tabindex="-1" class="btn btn-outline-secondary btn-sm rounded-0
pass_view" type="button"><i class="fa fa-eye-slash"></i></button>

    </div>

</div>

<div class="form-group">

    <label for="cpassword" class="control-label">Confirm Password</label>

    <div class="input-group input-group-sm">

        <input type="password" class="form-control form-control-sm rounded-0"
required="" id="cpassword">

        <button tabindex="-1" class="btn btn-outline-secondary btn-sm rounded-0
pass_view" type="button"><i class="fa fa-eye-slash"></i></button>

    </div>

</div>

</div>

<div class="col-lg-6 col-md-6 col-sm-12 col-xs-12">

    <div class="form-group">

        <label for="" class="control-label">Avatar</label>

        <div class="custom-file">

            <input type="file" class="custom-file-input rounded-0" id="customFile" name="img"
onchange="displayImg(this,$(this))" accept="image/png, image/jpeg">

            <label class="custom-file-label rounded-0" for="customFile">Choose file</label>

        </div>

    </div>

</div>

```

```

</div>

<div class="col-lg-6 col-md-6 col-sm-12 col-xs-12">

  <div class="form-group d-flex justify-content-center">

    

  </div>

  </div>

</div>

<div class="row">

  <div class="col-8">

    <a href="/login.php">Already hava an Account</a>

  </div>

  <!-- /.col -->

  <div class="col-4">

    <button type="submit" class="btn btn-primary btn-block">Create Account</button>

  </div>

  <!-- /.col -->

</div>

</form>

<!-- /.social-auth-links -->

<!-- <p class="mb-1">

  <a href="forgot-password.html">I forgot my password</a>

```

```

    </p> -->

</div>

<!-- /.card-body -->

</div>

<!-- /.card -->

</div>

<!-- /.login-box -->

</div>

<!-- jQuery -->

<script src="<?= base_url ?>plugins/jquery/jquery.min.js"></script>

<!-- Bootstrap 4 -->

<script src="<?= base_url ?>plugins/bootstrap/js/bootstrap.bundle.min.js"></script>

<!-- AdminLTE App -->

<script src="<?= base_url ?>dist/js/adminlte.min.js"></script>

<script>

function displayImg(input,_this) {
    if (input.files && input.files[0]) {
        var reader = new FileReader();
        reader.onload = function (e) {
            $('#cimg').attr('src', e.target.result);
        }
    }
}

```

```

        reader.readAsDataURL(input.files[0]);
    }else{
        $('#cimg').attr('src', "<?php echo validate_image(" ?>");
    }
}

$(document).ready(function(){
    end_loader();

    $('.pass_view').click(function(){
        var input = $(this).siblings('input')
        var type = input.attr('type')
        if(type == 'password'){
            $(this).html('<i class="fa fa-eye"></i>')
            input.attr('type','text').focus()
        }else{
            $(this).html('<i class="fa fa-eye-slash"></i>')
            input.attr('type','password').focus()
        }
    })

    $('#register-form').submit(function(e){
        e.preventDefault()
        var _this = $(this)
        var el = $('<div>')

```

```

    el.addClass('alert alert-danger err_msg')

    el.hide()

$('.err_msg').remove()

if($('#password').val() != $('#cpassword').val()){

    el.text('Password does not match')

    _this.prepend(el)

    el.show('slow')

    $('html, body').scrollTop(0)

    return false;

}

if(_this[0].checkValidity() == false){

    _this[0].reportValidity();

    return false;

}

start_loader()

$.ajax({

    url: _base_url_ + "classes/Users.php?f=registration",

    method:'POST',

    type:'POST',

    data:new FormData($(this)[0]),

    dataType:'json',

    cache:false,

    processData:false,

```

```

contentType: false,
error:err=>{
    console.log(err)
    alert('An error occurred')
    end_loader()
},
success:function(resp){
    if(resp.status == 'success'){
        location.href = ('./login.php')
    }else if (!!resp.msg){
        el.html(resp.msg)
        el.show('slow')
        _this.prepend(el)
        $('html, body').scrollTop(0)
    }else{
        alert('An error occurred')
        console.log(resp)
    }
    end_loader()
}
})
})
})

```

</script>

</body>

</html>